

Balinese Lexicons on Gamelan Musical Orchestra

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ABSTRACT: Ecolinguistics study concerned with the use of language and its environment. The existence of words or lexicons in the use by the speakers is due to the needs of the speakers of the language. The developments in technology have resulted in the disappearance of several previously existing lexicons, and new lexicons have emerged, resulting in previously existing lexicons being no longer known by the next generation, especially those who have switched professions to professions that are more economically or profitable. Tihingan Village is a village on Bali Island in which 60% of the population are *Pande* whose profession is as craftsmen making Gamelan Orchestra. Due to the recent development, some of the young generation shifted their profession to others. This research aimed to investigate the types of Balinese lexicons used by the *Pande* in their daily life during the production of musical orchestra products. The research was conducted in Tihingan village Klungkung Regency Bali Indonesia. It is field research, by direct observation and in-depth interviews with the *Pande* (craftsmen), a qualitative approach was applied to obtain the data, and the analysis was done descriptively. The findings show there were four types of lexicons found namely, lexicons related to materials, tools, processes, and products.

KEYWORDS: gamelan, lexicons, orchestra, *Tihingan* village.

INTRODUCTION

Bali as an island is very rich in culture, and though the preservation of culture is very important; modernization cannot be avoided. Related to language maintenance there are some shifts that happen in the social life of the Balinese people as they are exposed to modernization. To preserve the lexicons that are being used by the *Pande* in their daily life, this research is urgent to be done to document the lexicons that were being used by the *Pande* as their children no longer have the same profession as their parents. This research is conducted in Tihingan Village Klungkung Bali Indonesia. *Pande* residents in this village make various types of *gamelan*, so in their interactions, they involve a lot of special lexicon related to their work in producing products in the form of various types of *gamelan*, such as *gong*, *gender*, and *angklung*. This has a very high urgency to be carried out as a form of preserving and documenting the Balinese language.

Haugen (1972) reveals that language resides in the mind of the speaker and functions as a liaison between the speaker and the social and natural environment. The environment of a language is language speakers with social and cultural backgrounds because it is impossible to understand a language without its speakers. This is in accordance with the assessment of the vitality of language (UNESCO2003:1) which states that language differences are important for human heritage. Each language represents the unique cultural policies of its speakers so the extinction of a language is the destruction of its people. Economic developments, technology, and modernization have a major influence on the lexicon related to *memande* activities. Economically, many *Pande* residents switch professions to ones that are more economically profitable, technological developments result in changes in the tools used to carry out the activities, and modernization affects the types of products produced. This phenomenon has intrigued researchers to continue research on the Balinese lexicon, related to *Prapen* and *Memande* in Tihingan Village, Banjarangkan District, Klungkung Regency, Bali. Tihingan Village is a tourist village that produces *Gong*. *Pande* residents in this village make various types of *Gamelan*, therefore, in their interactions they involve a lot of special lexicon related to their work in producing products in the form of various types of *gamelan*, such as: *gong*, *gender*, and *angklung*. This has a very high urgency to be carried out as a form of preserving and documenting the Balinese language. The problems raised in the research was, how were the Balinese lexicons grouped, and related to *Prapen* and *Memande gamelan*? This research is very important to carry out because research can quickly see the conditions of the use of the lexicon related to *Prapen* and *memande gamelan*, which is one of the language domains specifically related to the environment (ecolinguistics) of language use when making Balinese musical instruments, including

gamelan which is done by Pande residents in Tihingan village. All lexicons related to these matters need to be documented according to daily use by Pande residents, as well as recording previously existing lexicons that are now rarely used by them.

Subianto, Agus (2013) in his article entitled *Ekolinguistik Model dan Penerapannya* (Ecolinguistic Model and its Application) states that Social praxis, which includes dimensions of biological, sociological, and ideological have interrelation with language. Language influence and at that moment simultaneously influenced by social praxis. The dialectical relationship between language and This social praxis has given birth to studies of dialectical or dialectical linguistics or ecolinguistics. Four theoretical framework models of dialectical linguistics has been developed by Bang and Door (1993) namely the dialogue model, the deixis model, model semantic matrix, and the core contradiction model. The first three models can be applied to analyze text. In perspective dialectical linguistics, the text is in a dialogical situation, and for that, the text must be analyzed based on its function, which includes inter-textuality, intra-textuality, and extra-textuality. These three texts function in line with the principle of dialectical linguistics which states that every individuality, including the text, resides within three interconnected dimensions, viz ideological, sociological, and biological dimensions.

Supatmiwati, et.al (2021) in their article `An Ecolinguistic study on eco spirituals Tourism of Rebo Buntung Commodification` claim that cultural forms and elements possess the potential to serve as commodities in the realm of tourism, implying their commodification. The authenticity of a culture can be adjusted to appeal to tourists, ensuring a concealed authenticity, regardless of the scale. Transforming cultural rituals into tourism commodities becomes a method of preserving culture and language, even as they are adapted for tourism purposes. Consequently, the religious-cultural structure of Rebo Buntung and Tetulaq Tamperan should be presented with an original model showcasing traditional practices, serving as a medium for preserving culture and language. Simultaneously, contextual practices adapted to the tourism industry should be incorporated to attract tourists. This spiritual eco-commodification aims to boost the economy of the local community. In essence, the adoption of eco-spiritual commodification is anticipated to create a ripple effect, not only safeguarding culture and language but also fostering harmony between the community and nature, while enhancing the local economy.

Yuniawan, Tommi (2018) claims the study of ecolinguistics in conservation news texts in Indonesian mass media yields theoretical and practical benefits. It provides a descriptive analysis of linguistic units, encompassing ideological, sociological, and biological dimensions. Additionally, it offers instructional materials in the form of news texts, particularly conservation news text—a genre aligning with basic competencies in the curriculum. Furthermore, it contributes to interdisciplinary consolidation by strengthening the theories and methods of journalistic and linguistic studies. Lastly, it offers insights to media managers for presenting conservation news realistically and serves as input for news sources when interacting with the media.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The research was conducted at Tihingan Village Klungkung Bali. The data of the research were taken from direct observation, interviews in depth with the Orchestra Craftsmen (Pande Gamelan), and documentation methods. The informants were the resource persons from where the data were collected, they were the Pande and their employees. The selection of the informant applying purposive sampling, by selecting the key informant (head of the village) as he knows more about the condition of the Orchestra maker (Pande Gamelan).

The technique of observation and interviews with the informants in depth was conducted to obtain more information related to the lexicons of Gamelan. They are related to the process, the products, materials, and tools

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The observations results and interviews with the informants of the Orchestra craftsmen (Pande Gamelan) there were about 60 % of the villagers worked as craftsmen whether as the owners of the Orchestra Producers or just as employees. Some of the younger generations have shifted their profession into different fields such as working at the government office, as teachers, doctors, and in the hospitality business. These give a different condition to the prior modernization in this village, therefore this also gave impact to the use of the lexicons related to the gamelan Orchestra, as they mingled in other fields. Based on the result of the research there were four types of Balinese lexicons namely lexicon of process, products, materials, and tools. These lexicons are presented in Tables 1 to 4

The process lexicons are Balinese lexicons that are used by the Pande when they conduct the process of making the Orchestra, these process lexicons are presented in Table 1 below.

Table 1

Balinese Lexicons related to the process		
No	Balinese	English (gloss translation)
1	<i>nyuring</i>	to bend smaller piece of metal
2	<i>ngantil</i>	to hit the metal piece
3	<i>manggur</i>	to
4	<i>matutan</i>	to harmonize the sound
5	<i>moncolin</i>	to
6	<i>ngebor</i>	to drill
7	<i>ngempug</i>	to split
8	<i>ngerinda</i>	to smoothen
9	<i>ngergaji</i>	to saw
10	<i>ngetep</i>	to cut
11	<i>nyeep</i>	to cool down the temperature of the metal

Balinese lexicon related to the process of making Gamelan Orchestra, table 2 below shows the lexicons related to the process

Table 2

Balinese Lexicons Related to the Products	
No	Balinese
1	<i>Anteg-anteg</i>
2	<i>bebende</i>
3	<i>Bilah gangsa</i>
4	<i>cengceng</i>
5	<i>curing</i>
6	<i>Gambelan jegogan</i>
7	<i>getungtangan</i>
8	<i>Gong</i>
9	<i>Kendang keruntung</i>
10	<i>reong</i>

Some of the products of the Pande are presented below

gong

Cengceng

reong

Set of the Gamelan Complete

Pemade

Balinese lexicons related to tools in making Gamelan Orchestra is presented in Table 3

Table 3

Balinese Lexicons related to tools		
No	Balinese	English (gloss translation)
1	<i>Batu pemoncolan</i>	wide form of stone to smoothen the metal
2	<i>Bor tangan</i>	drill
3	<i>Cetakan bilah</i>	<i>bilah</i> based form
4	<i>Cetakan reong</i>	<i>reong</i> based form
5	<i>Culik api</i>	metal holder
6	<i>Gergaji mesin</i>	saw
7	<i>gerinda</i>	grinder
8	<i>Sepit</i>	tongs
9	<i>kuas</i>	paintbrush
10	<i>landesan</i>	metal base
11	<i>palu</i>	hammer

The following are some pictures of the tools used to produce Gamelan

landesan

palu penampel

cetakan reong

culik api

Balinese Lexicons related to materials used in making the Gamelan Orchestra are present in the following table (4)

Table 4

Materials used in making the products		
No	Balinese	English (gloss translation)
1	<i>adeng</i>	charcoal
2	<i>blulang</i>	leather
3	<i>cat</i>	paint
4	<i>perunggu</i>	bronze
5	<i>jangat</i>	type of wood
6	<i>kayu jati</i>	teak wood
7	<i>kayu nangka</i>	jackfruit wood
8	<i>ketewel</i>	type of wood
9	<i>lak lakan</i>	based form
10	<i>perada</i>	golden paint
11	<i>tiing</i>	bamboo

CONCLUSION

Based on the research result there were found four types of Balinese lexicons related to Balinese Gamelan Orchestra i.e.; Balinese lexicons on Process, Balinese lexicons on Products, Balinese lexicons on materials, and Balinese lexicons on tools. The use of lexicons related to Memande Gamelan at *Tihingan* Village is mostly related to the environment of the occupation of the *Pande* (Gamelan Orchestra craftsmen)

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